

Quantification of resilience in farm animals

Taghipoor^{M1}, Pastell M², Martin O¹, Nguyen ba H³, van Milgen J⁴, Doesch-Wilson A⁵, Loncke C¹, Friggens NC¹, Puillet L¹, Muñoz-Tamayo R¹

¹Université Paris-Saclay, INRAE, AgroParisTech, UMR Modélisation Systémique Appliquée aux Ruminants, 91120, Palaiseau, France

²Natural Resources Institute Finland (Luke), Production Systems, Helsinki, Finland

³Univ Clermont Auvergne, INRAE, VetAgro Sup, UMR Herbivores, F-63122 Saint Genes Champanelle, France

⁴Inst Agro, PEGASE, INRAE, Paris, France

⁵Univ Edinburgh, Roslin Inst, Edinburgh EH25 9RG, Scotland

Corresponding author: Masoomeh Taghipoor (Masoomeh.Taghipoor@inrae.fr)

Abstract. Resilience, when defined as the capacity of an animal to respond to short term environmental challenges and to return to the pre-challenge status, is a dynamic and complex trait. Resilient animals contribute to reinforce the capacity of the herd to cope with often fluctuating and unpredictable environmental conditions. Quantification of resilience at individual scale enables potentially including this trait into future breeding programs, for the animals with a better capacity to adapt to the changing environment, and therefore potentially reduce the risk for disease and improve the welfare of animals.

The ability of modern technologies for longitudinal monitoring of multiple indicators of animal performance, at individual scale is a huge step forward to evaluate resilience of farm animals. Resilience is not directly measurable and the development of interpretive models is necessary to quantify indicators associated with resilience. In addition to the quantification of resilience capacity, another application of models described in this paper are detection of periods of perturbations as perceived by the animal, which helps the farmer to adapt an adequate management strategy to help the animal coping with the perturbation, and in this way reducing the use of medicines, and decrease the level of the pain of the animal. These applications do not require explicit knowledge of the origin of the perturbations, and are developed with case studies in real-time and post-treatment of data.

The main objective of this paper is to illustrate with examples, different modeling approaches to get the most out of this new generation of data (i.e., with high frequency recording) to detect and quantify animals' responses to perturbations. In addition, perspectives on the use of hybrid models for better understanding and predicting animal resilience are presented.

Keywords. Resilience, welfare, farm animals, Precision Livestock Farming (PLF), hybrid modeling

Implications

Quantification of resilience capacity at individual scale is useful for the optimization of future breeding programs, for the animals with a better capacity to adapt to the changing environment. However, resilience is a complex and dynamic trait which is not directly measurable. New monitoring technologies from Precision Livestock Farming (PLF) increased the number of data collected in farms. In this study, we present two modelling approaches (based on real time or offline treatments of data) to analyse these data and evaluate the resilience capacity at individual scale. These models enable also the detection of environmental perturbations as perceived by the animal, which is useful for farmers to adapt an adequate management strategy to help the animal coping with the perturbation, and in this way reducing the use of medicines, and decrease the level of the pain of the animal.

Introduction

During the last decades, there has been an explosion in the number of sensors in the context of precision livestock farming (PLF). Sensors such as cameras, microphones and accelerometers made

possible to monitor animals automatically and individually in real time (Halachmi et al., 2019; Caja et al., 2020; Gómez et al., 2021) and with a lower cost (Wolfert et al., 2017). These new monitoring technologies have increased exponentially the number of data collected and therefore our capacity to observe animals. The data obtained from these devices can be of great interest for farmers and the livestock sector to improve production, animal health and animal welfare, while reducing the impact of livestock on the environment (Friggens et al., 2008; Højsgaard and Friggens, 2010).

The interpretation of this increasing quantity of heterogeneous data generated by sensors is a major challenge (González et al., 2018; Morota et al., 2018; Tedeschi, 2019; Ellis et al., 2020). It implies for animal scientists the need to acquire new skills in data processing and consolidate multidisciplinary collaborations. In this context, mathematical modeling is a powerful tool that allows the analysis of these data and added insight in their interpretation. Combination of records of such sensors with adequate data analysis algorithms and models helps for monitoring welfare and predicting productivity of animals (Werkheiser, 2018; Benjamin and Yik, 2019).

The capacity of modern technologies to monitor automatically and simultaneously multiple traits from sensors with high frequency at individual scale is a huge step forward to study resilience of farm animals. This dynamic trait is of great interest for farming systems, as resilient animals contribute to reinforce the capacity of the herd to cope with fluctuating and unpredictable environmental conditions (Dumont et al., 2014). One of the definition of resilience is the capacity to respond to short term environmental (temperature, sanitary stress, etc) challenges and to be able to return rapidly to the pre-challenge status (Colditz and Hine, 2016). Many other definitions of resilience and related concepts (e.g. plasticity, robustness, GxE interactions) can be found in the literature (Berghof et al., 2019b). Their common point is that they all refer to resilience as a complex property to be measured from the responses of various traits to a perturbation (Friggens et al., 2022). The evaluation of the resilience is also useful in the machine learning algorithms for the early prediction of the resilience capacity, by using the non-invasive indicators of the animals' response to environmental and physiological challenges. Such an algorithm helps the farmer to adapt an adequate strategy to help animals to cope with different types of perturbations (for example by using pharmaceutical treatments).

In general, the dynamic response of the animal to a perturbation can be decomposed into a first period in which the animal try limit the impact of the disturbing factor on its performance and a second period for the animal to recover once the perturbing factor is over (Doeschl-Wilson, 2011; Mulder and Rashidi, 2017; Scheffer et al., 2018; Knap and Doeschl-Wilson, 2020). Some authors considered that there is a latency period, e.g. at the beginning of an infection, during which the perturbing factor is present with no impact on animal performance (Sandberg et al., 2006; Sauvant and Martin, 2010).

The response of the animal to a perturbing factor is a function of both animals' adaptive capacity and the magnitude of the perturbing factor. Time-series data from sensors reflect animals' responses faced with different types of disturbing factors (with known or unknown origins) using measured performance traits. To quantify the resilience of animals, a first step is to define the currency or a metric for the animal's response and transform the concept of resilience into measurable variables (Todman et al., 2016; Ingrisch and Bahn, 2018). In the definition of this metric, factors such as the nature and the number of indicators of performance, and the research question should be considered (Fig. 1). Table 1 represents some of these metrics and their use in the context of animal adaptive response.

Figure 1. A hypothetical example of the response of three animals to a given perturbation. Animals' observable response started at the time T1. The recovery started at the time T2. Animal **a** has a largest decrease in performance but recovers faster, while animal **b** and **c** have a smaller decrease in performance but they recover later. Moreover, animal **c** seems to compensate for the loss of performance. It is therefore necessary to define metrics for animal's resilience capacity to phenotype animals based on the same criteria.

Mathematical models are powerful tools to put together theoretical frameworks, existing knowledge and available data to provide new insights on unknown phenomena. Tedeschi (2019) made an exhaustive synthesis on different types of mathematical models used in animal nutrition. When knowledge on the mechanisms underlying the system behaviour is available, the construction of mathematical models is derived by using established principles (*e.g.*, law of conservation of mass). For these models, the parameters are expected to be interpretable (*i.e.*, to have biological meaning) (Lema-Perez et al., 2019). In cases where knowledge is lacking, mathematical models are used to extract empirical information from data recorded from different performance traits, at different levels (cells, blood plasma, animal, etc). They thus contribute to identifying new principles governing system behaviour.

Inputs, parameters and outputs are the main components of dynamic models (Figure 2). The main role of a modeller is to specify the structure of the models and to determine the parameters that describe the characteristics of the system under study (animal). In what are called "forward problems", given a model structure, inputs and parameters' values, the model predicts outputs. In contrast to the forward problem, the inverse problem is a mathematical framework that allows obtaining information on model parameters, given the model structure and the available data from observations or measurements of animal response. The inverse problem needs to address both theoretical and practical challenges for identifying accurately the model parameters and thus providing adequate predictive power (Muñoz-Tamayo et al., 2018; Vargas-Villamil et al., 2020). This approach is used in the literature to quantify individuals' resilience defined as a parameter in perturbation models (Nguyen-Ba et al., 2020; Ben Abdelkrim et al., 2021a). Doeschl-Wilson et al. (2007) showed that in case of animal models, these parameters can be used in the context of genetic selection, because they can be defined so as to represent the genotype of the animal, independent of the environment.

With respect to data frequency and existing knowledge on underlying mechanisms, there are two main categories of models to characterize animal's adaptive response. The first category is concept-driven or mechanistic models considering the systemic aspect of animal's response, and the second category is models based on data called data-driven models. Both categories have been often used to understand animals' adaptive response, in particular when faced with nutritional challenges. Ellis et al. (2020) suggested that in the future modern animal production systems will take advantage of hybrid models including both data driven and concept driven approaches.

The main objective of this paper is to illustrate how mathematical models can adapt to this new

generation of data (i.e., with high frequency record) to quantify animal's response to perturbations, and in this way to contribute to a better understanding of animal resilience capacity. In addition, perspectives on the use of hybrid models for better understanding and predicting animal resilience are presented. Our discussions are supported by case studies. Models were implemented in the free software R (R version 3.4.2, <https://www.r-project.org/>). To promote open science practices (Muñoz-Tamayo et al., 2022) and facilitate the understanding of the modelling approaches, the R code of the examples are available at <https://quantanimal.github.io/>.

1. Perturbations and the theoretical trajectory of performance

When developing a model to describe an animal's response to short-term perturbations, the first step is to determine what is called a perturbation. A perturbation in the context of this study consists of all short-term changes in the farm environment, such as temperature, feed compositions, presence of a pathogen, etc, that impact animals' performance.

The second step is to consider the available indicators of performance impacted by these perturbations, and to determine the theoretical trajectory associated to these indicators. The theoretical trajectory is defined as the performance of the animal in the absence of all perturbations in the environment (Nguyen-Ba et al., 2019). For farm animals, the theoretical trajectory of performance depends on the long-term environment, animal genetics and feeding strategy. Finally, deviations (positive or negative) from this trajectory can then be quantified as the impact of perturbation (one should make sure that detected deviations are not part of inherent variations of the animal behaviour). Depending on the available data, one or several indicators of performance could be used to quantify the animal's adaptive response (Table 1).

2. From classical to a new generation of models

Since the 1970s, several concept-driven models have been developed to study the effect of feed composition and feed availability on animal performance (Whittemore and Fawcett, 1976; Whittemore, 1986; van Milgen et al., 2008; Martin and Sauvant, 2010; Puillet et al., 2016). These models are typically based on concepts of a performance potential, nutrient partitioning and efficiency of nutrient utilization (i.e., input-output relationships). There are also a few models considering the influence of other environmental changes on animal performance (Wellock et al., 1998; Sandberg et al., 2006; Doeschl-Wilson et al., 2009). The small number of such models is likely due to difficulties in characterizing the environment and the multiple traits with which the animal responds to environmental changes. These models are forward problems, in which, given a model structure, the inputs (ex. feed composition, frequency, environment) and parameters' values (growth rate, feed efficiency, etc), the user can predict the outputs (body weight, number of offspring, etc). The common denominator of these models is that they are concept-driven (Figure 2).

When data are available, but knowledge on the underlying mechanisms responsible for the loss in performance is missing or not needed, statistical and computational tools are used, with minimum information on these mechanisms. These approaches are about developing models based on data recorded dynamically (in the case of adaptive response) and the effort of the modeller is to determine the function that mimics the evolution of a trait over time. Such approaches have been used, for example, to describe the body weight of growing pigs by Gompertz function (Schulin-Zeuthen et al., 2008; Lewis and Emmans, 2020), or cumulative feed intake by Gamma function (van Milgen et al., 2008), or infection profiles of pigs (Islam et al., 2013).

During recent years, the application fields of such classical approaches were evolved to get most out of the new generation of data coming from the precision livestock farming (Yu et al., 2021). For example, the concept-driven models are usually used to test different hypotheses (forward problem, Figure 2) as inputs of the model and observe the impacts on the outputs, in presence of easily available dynamic outputs (indicators of performance). Although, such applications are still relevant, such

models can be used in inverse problems to determine parameters of the models which represents individual's capacity response (Doeschl-Wilson et al., 2007; Yu et al., 2021).

Figure 2. Difference in the concept of forward and inverse problems. a. the forward problem is the use of the models to predict the response of the animal (outputs) to a stimuli (inputs), given the animal characteristics (parameters) and a model structure (representation of underlying mechanisms or input-output behaviour). b. In the case of inverse problem, the time-series data of model outputs can be measured. Then given these data, and model structure, the user can estimate the characteristic of the animal (model parameters), using an adequate optimization procedure.

Evolution in data driven approaches to quantify animal resilience are in particular related to the availability of performance data at high frequency and for a large number of animals. This new generation of data opened new horizons for the real-time treatment of individuals. It uses the animal as its own control, which is a huge progress for the respect of animals' welfare as performance measures are adjusted to the individual (Sun et al., 2010; Kamphuis et al., 2010). The detection of early signs of health problems allows the farmer to adapt an adequate management strategy to help the animal coping with that problem, and consequently to reduce the use of medicine and antibiotic (Jørgensen et al., 2016), which will contribute to a better respect of animal welfare by decreasing the level of pain associated with that disease. The objectives of such modelling approaches are the detection of perturbations in real time and helping at providing correct management strategy or medical treatments on time. To go further toward applications, such models are often implemented in decision support systems to optimize the decision of the farmers, and suggest the best treatment in relation with a detected perturbation (Rutter, 2014; Van Nuffel et al., 2015; Stygar et al., 2021).

In what follows, examples of models are described to detect and quantify the animals' capacity of response to perturbations. These models are separated into two categories of applications: models for post-treatment of data, and models for real-time treatment of data. Although, examples are not exhaustive and other modelling approaches exist, they reflect the way that the classical modelling approaches were evolved to consider the high frequency records of performance data. Moreover, we discuss the interest of coupling such approaches and moving towards hybrid models and processes, in which one can predict the resilience capacity of animals.

3. Post-treatment of longitudinal data

Defining or finding a function that fits the perturbed data with a rather good accuracy is the main difficulty when studying performance trajectories during perturbation periods. Some popular functions such as Gompertz (Schulin-Zeuthen et al., 2008) to describe theoretical growth of farm animals and Wood (Wood, 1967) for the theoretical milk yield of dairy cows in non-limiting

environments, are largely used by animal scientists and modellers. Despite the usefulness of these functions to represent the time-trends of these traits, they cannot fit the evolution of data during the perturbed periods. Some of these functions were modified to account for the potential periods of perturbation. For example the modified Gompertz function (Golubev, 2009), considers the possibility of deviations from Gompertz function to describe the influence of the perturbation on the performance. It was used successfully to quantify piglet robustness at weaning (Revilla et al., 2019). A modified wood function was used to simulate the milk yield in presence of environmental and nutritional perturbations (Ben Abdelkrim et al., 2021a). Some authors suggested the use of the well-known physical spring and damper system to mimic animal adaptive response (Sadoul et al., 2015; Todman et al., 2016; Taghipoor et al., 2017).

These models are built with few conceptual aspects, and their main interest is the characterization of the biologically meaningful parameters to quantify the animal's response to the perturbation. This is in contrast to the classical concept driven models, in which the underlying mechanisms of the response are considered as much as possible. In the models described here, inputs and outputs are recorded and the objective is the estimation of model parameters (inverse problem, Figure 2). In such models, the first step is the development of a module illustrating the expected trajectory of the performance in a long-term stable environment, and subsequently add the perturbation module to characterize animal's response, for example, developing a perturbation module to describe deviations from the expected trajectory of feed intake for growing pigs (Nguyen-Ba et al., 2020).

Although functions discussed in previous paragraphs have parameters that can be used as metrics for animal responses, the question arises what to do if the time-trend of the response cannot be described by the already defined, or known, functions or systems of equations. This is especially pertinent, when the shape of the expected trajectory is unknown. If available data are recorded at high frequency, a purely data-driven model could be used to describe an animal's capacity of response. One of these methods is differential smoothing of time-series measurements, termed functional data analysis (Ramsay and Silverman, 2002; Codrea et al., 2011; Ben Abdelkrim et al., 2021b). The combination of this approach with other regression methods such as quantile regression makes it possible to estimate the expected trajectory of the performance and detect the perturbation periods (Scheffer et al., 2018; Berghof et al., 2019b; a; Poppe et al., 2020; Nguyen-Ba et al., 2020; Adriaens et al., 2020). To illustrate different approaches for post-treatment of longitudinal performance data, two case studies are developed. Although, in these examples the expected trajectory of performance is considered as known, different methods exist to estimate it from perturbed performance data, in the case that it was unknown.

Case study 1. Dynamic model with biologically meaningful parameters. The perturbation started at t_j^b and was over at t_j^e , and during this period it decreased the performance $y(t)$. To describe the intensity of animal's response to perturbations, let's assume that Equation 1 describes the variation of the intensity of the perturbation

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{d\alpha_j}{dt} = k_{1j}(-\alpha_j) * \mathbb{1}_j(t) + k_{2j}(1 - \alpha_j) (1 - \mathbb{1}_j(t)) \\ \alpha_j(t^b) = 1 \\ \mathbb{1}_j(t) = 1, \text{ for } t_j^b \leq t \leq t_j^e \end{array} \right. \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

Where k_{1j} and k_{2j} are model parameters and characterize the animal's response to perturbation j in term of loss of the performance and recovery capacity, respectively. $\mathbb{1}_j(t)$ is the identity function which is one during the perturbation interval and 0, elsewhere. The value $\alpha_j(t^b)$ stands for the initial value

of the function α_j . Therefore, the function α_j is one in non-perturbed conditions and less than one during the perturbation periods. Then the trajectory of animal performance $y(t)$ during n perturbations can be described as Equation 2.

$$\begin{cases} y(t) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \alpha_j(t) * f(P, t), \\ y(t_0) = f(P, t_0) = y_0, \end{cases} \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

Where $f(P, t)$ describes the theoretical function of animal performance, P is the set of model parameters describing the characteristics of the theoretical trajectory, t is time interval of experiment.

The set of parameters that characterize the animal's response to these two perturbations are (k_{1j}, k_{2j}) and the time interval of perturbation j ($\Delta t_j = t_j^s - t_j^b$), where t_j^b and t_j^s are the time of the beginning and the end of the perturbing factor. In the case where the periods of perturbations are not reported, the perturbation time parameter values can be estimated. Figure 3 shows the estimation of theoretical curve of performance, the perturbation intervals and their dynamic using this model.

Given the fact that the development of the model is based on knowledge on the shape of the response, i.e. decrease followed by an increase, we can consider the model as based on existing knowledge. However, the use of this model requires the availability of longitudinal data with high frequency, and in this respect, it is useful only if such data are available.

Figure 3. Hypothetic example of animal response to two different perturbations. Two consecutive perturbations occurred at time $t_1^b = 10$ and $t_2^b = 75$, and were over at $t_1^s = 25$ and $t_2^s = 85$ days of age. Parameters of animal's response (k_{1j}, k_{2j}) are $(0.05, 0.15)$ for the first perturbation and $(0.1, 0.05)$ for the second. One can observe that the animal had a better capacity to resist faced with the first perturbation, while the capacity of recovery was better in the second perturbation. Moreover, compared to the second perturbation (10 days), the animal took more time to start the recovery period in the first perturbation (15 days).

Case study 2. Differential smoothing model.

This example shows the use of a purely data-driven approach for the post treatment of performance data under perturbations. Figure 4 shows a hypothetical example, in which the expected performance is equal to 1, and the deviations from this value could be considered as perturbations. Data were smoothed using B-Spline bases of order 5 with the roughness penalty ($\lambda = 10^4$) to estimate animal performance (<https://quantanimal.github.io/>). Three features are used to characterize the animal's

response to the perturbation i : the area between the theoretical trajectory and the perturbed curve (A_i), the maximum amplitude of deviation from the theoretical performance (h_i), and the duration of perturbation (ΔT_i). These criteria allowed comparison of the animal's responses to each of the perturbations, and also, in the case of larger number of animals, to rank animals for their adaptive capacity. Other features such as the maximum decrease and increase rates (zeros of the second derivative) could also be extracted using function derivatives. Table 2 shows values of different defined features for the hypothetic example of figure 4, which shows two deviations from the theoretical trajectory of performance. Since a deviation could be part of the inherent behaviour of the animal, one needs to determine the criteria that are used to classify a deviation as perturbation, such as the length and the magnitude of a deviation (Nguyen-Ba et al., 2020). Another criterion is the determination of common periods of deviations among all animals in a pen, that suggests that the origin of the perturbations is in the farm environment (Ben Abdelkrim et al., 2021a).

This approach with the use of function's derivatives is particularly useful, in the case of studying large number of animals, to automatize the individual analyses of performance data and the detection and quantification of perturbations. For example, in the case of Figure 4, the beginning of a perturbation is when the perturbed curve of the performance deviates negatively from the theoretical performance, usually after a local maximum, which can be easily detected by calculating the derivative of the perturbed curve. The end of a perturbation is a local minimum of the perturbed curve (when the recovery starts), and is associated to the zeros of the derivative, where it changes from negative to positives values.

Figure 4. Estimation of animal's performance using differential smoothing. The upper graph shows the estimated function (black curve) against observation (dots). The lower graph shows the derivative of the estimated function. Zeros of derivatives are associated with maximums and minimums of the function. The blue line on the upper graph shows the theoretical performance of the animal, which is assumed to be 1. A_i , h_i and ΔT_i are the area under the perturbed curve, the maximum effect of the perturbation and the time duration of the perturbation, respectively.

4. Real-time treatment of data

In this section, we discuss the mathematical and statistical methods for real time detection of perturbations, in which the models use real time data for detecting and quantifying perturbations. Real time detection is commonly used in early warning systems where the aim is to detect for example sick animals to initiate treatment as early as possible (Dominiak and Kristensen, 2017). In addition to detect the occurrence of a perturbation, it can be useful to quantify the magnitude of the animal's response and thereby to plan the correct veterinary treatment or management action such as adjustment of feeding.

Using state-space models and observers to detect perturbations

In the state-space modeling approach to time series, it is assumed that the development of a system is associated with latent states described by a series of state vectors θ_t which are associated to observations y_t and control inputs u_t . The relation between θ_t and y_t is specified by a state space model such that the system state at time t contains all the information necessary to predict future values of y_t . As an example, animals' activity level for the next hours or days can be forecasted using estimated mean, slope and periodic components based on activity measurements.

A system can be represented in state-space model form using the differential equation (or equivalent difference equation):

$$\frac{d\theta}{dt} = f(\theta, u, P), \quad y = h(\theta, u, P), \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

where P is the parameter vector, the function f determines the rate of change of the state vector as a function of state θ and control, and the function h gives the measured values as functions of state and control (Astrom and Murray, 2008).

In the contrary to the models for post-treatment of data, one of the challenges in real-time approaches is related to knowledge on the individual theoretical trajectory of performance. In such cases, hypotheses on the theoretical trajectory are tested, and often known functions such as polynomials are used. Regarding to the availability of the theoretical trajectory, two case studies of the use of state-space modeling are presented.

Case study 3. Known theoretical trajectory.

In this example, we show the use of state observers to quantify dynamic perturbations. An observer is an object that combines a mathematical model and on-line data to estimate unmeasured variables (Dochain, 2003). For our case study, we aim to use real-time records of body weight to extract information on the perturbation that an animal is facing. For that, we assume that the theoretical trajectory of growth follows a Gompertz function. This example is inspired by the work of Revilla et al. (2019).

The following equation describes the dynamic of the body weight (y) in presence of perturbations

$$\frac{dy(t)}{dt} = -\varphi \cdot y + y \cdot p_1 \cdot e^{-p_2 \cdot t} \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

The term φ is assumed to be unknown and represents a dynamic perturbation factor that explains the deviations from the expected trajectory. If $\varphi = 0$, Equation 4 is the classical Gompertz model with parameters p_1, p_2 (assumed to be known) .

We are then interested in estimating the dynamic perturbation factor $\varphi(t)$. This estimation can be done by the following extended model:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\hat{y}}{dt} &= -\hat{\varphi} * y + y * p_1 * e^{-p_2 t} + \omega_1 (y - \hat{y}) \\ \frac{d\hat{\varphi}}{dt} &= -\omega_2 * y * (y - \hat{y}) \end{aligned} \quad \text{Equation 5}$$

This extended mode is called a state observer or software sensor. Here, \hat{y} is the estimation of y and $\hat{\varphi}$ is the estimation of φ . The dynamics of the estimated variables is driven by the observation error ($y - \hat{y}$). The parameters ω_1, ω_2 are the design parameters of the observer which are chosen to set desired properties of the error dynamics. For example, we are interested in setting adequate values to make that the error reaches rapidly the zero value.

To illustrate the observer-based estimator, we generated simulated data for 80 days by setting a piecewise constant function for the perturbation term, $\varphi = 0.1, \text{ if } t \in [2 \ 10], \varphi = 0.05, \text{ if } t \in [40 \ 45]$ and $\varphi = 0$, elsewhere. The model parameters were set to $p_1 = 0.05 \text{ d}^{-1}, p_2 = 0.02 \text{ d}^{-1}$. The tuning parameters were set to $\omega_1 = 4.0, \omega_2 = 0.5$.

Figure 5 shows the comparison between the online data (y) and the estimated body weight (\hat{y}). The figure also shows the estimated $\hat{\varphi}$. Note that the observer did not require the information of the time at which the perturbations occurred. The trajectory of $\hat{\varphi}$ can be used to detect the perturbation times. In addition of providing different characteristics of the perturbation, $\hat{\varphi}$ can be used further to construct a model with an explicit function of the perturbation. This can be done using either mechanistic, empirical or hybrid models (Chen et al., 2000). The main limitation of the approach is the need of establishing known functions of the expected trajectory of performance, which is a challenging task.

Figure 5. A. Comparison of the real online trajectory of body weight (y) (●) against the estimated trajectory (\hat{y}) by the observer (solid line). B. Estimated trajectory $\hat{\varphi}$ by the observer (solid line) compared with the real trajectory φ (●). Note that in practice the real trajectory φ is unknown. In the example, we can plot it because it was set by construction.

Case study 4. Unknown theoretical trajectory. In the previous example, the theoretical trajectory of animal performance was assumed to be known. Another approach based on state-space models is to estimate the expected trajectory and the impact of perturbation on it in real time using a dynamic linear model (DLM). A DLM is a linear and discrete Gaussian state space model specified with a pair of difference equations (Equation 5) (West and Harrison, 1997; Petris et al., 2009).

DLMs are often used to detect when the state of the animal is perturbed in online monitoring applications. The objective of this method is an online estimate of the theoretical trajectory $f(P, t)$ and forecasting future values $f(P, t + k)$. A common method to detect perturbation is to inspect the model forecast errors. This approach involves finding the right DLM for online estimation of the theoretical trajectory $f(P, t)$ of the system, forecasting the expected trajectory, k steps ahead and comparing the forecast error to the observed value. If the forecast estimates drift away from zero, we conclude that a perturbation (a change point) has occurred, and the estimate for the magnitude of perturbation can be obtained from the residual. This principle was used by Stygar et al. (2018) for detecting perturbations from pig's growth using frequent weight measurements. Their model also incorporated a diurnal component in the system model using trigonometric functions.

The approaches using a single DLM work for detecting changes from the expected trajectory, however they provide limited use for characterizing the perturbation. In the presence of perturbations, the dynamics of the system often change, requiring the use of a different model to estimate the perturbed state. Switching DLMs provide a method for detecting regime shifts in real-time and modeling systems with several dynamic regimes. These models can also be called multiprocess class I models, switching linear dynamical systems, or multiple model algorithms (Gustafsson, 2000; Norberg et al., 2008).

We revisit the problem presented in the differential smoothing section by estimating the perturbations from data presented in Figure 5 using a switching model. We use one dynamic model for the unperturbed state and a separate model for the perturbed state, and a discrete latent variable $s_t \in \{\text{unperturbed, perturbed}\}$ indicates which model is active at each time. By observing the data we see that in the unperturbed state the series has a constant mean and in the perturbed state there is clear change in the slope. We model the unperturbed state using a local level model (1st order polynomial) and the perturbed state using a local linear trend model (2nd order polynomial). Figure 6 shows the state estimate for both models, the probability of each being active and the estimated slope for the second order model. The linear trend model has higher posterior probability during the perturbations and provides an online estimate of timing of perturbations that can be used to make management decisions. The online estimate of slope has similar shape to one provided by the differential smoothing method in Figure 5.

Figure 6. Example of using a switching model for detecting perturbations. The series is filtered using two different filters: 1st order model representing unperturbed dynamics and 2nd order model representing perturbed dynamics. The second panel shows the posterior probability for each model being the correct at time t and the bottom panel shows the estimated slope based on the second order model.

Altogether, these two case studies showed that the availability of high frequency performance data enables the use of existing statistical methods for the real time treatment of animal's response at individual level.

Discussion and perspectives

The objective of this work was to show with examples how the combination of data from new monitoring technologies and adequate mathematical models enables the quantification of the animal's responses faced with short term environmental challenges.

In this work the models were separated into two categories, concept-driven and data-driven models, and the usefulness of each of them were described. Data-driven models have often been assigned the name black box models for which forecasting is possible. In this respect, models considering the underlying mechanisms of animal's response could be considered as white box models. In the era of big data and powerful computing machines, it is unrealistic to focus on only one of these approaches, in particular, to study animal's resilience, which is a complex trait. The combination of these two approaches will lead to so called "grey box" or hybrid models, for which a part of a priori knowledge is considered (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Hybrid modelling approach takes advantage of both data- and concept-driven models to extract the maximum information from existing data.

One of the main input mechanisms to data-driven models for real-time detection of perturbations is the determination of the theoretical trajectory of a trait, for which, only perturbed data are available. Including knowledge on the shape of the expected trajectory (a simple example is the increasing function for growth, or an increasing plateau for feed intake), makes its estimation more realistic. For example, in the case of long-lasting perturbations, a purely data-driven method considers the perturbation as part of normal response of the animal, or will underestimate its impact. This then leads to the need for a theoretical reference curve, based on mechanisms. It is worth mentioning that the integration of the mechanisms may change based on how much details is required for the model. For example, in the case of detection of perturbations, only the shape of the expected trajectory of performance is enough, while for real-time prediction of animal's capacity of resilience more mechanisms could be required. In the latter case, a mechanistic model of animals' response combined with a data-driven approach for online prediction may help at prediction of individuals' resilience capacity.

The use of hybrid models is a key aspect to tackle the innate multivariate aspect of resilience. Interpreting time-series data on one dimension of animal performance (for instance milk production, body weight) is a necessary first step. However, to achieve a comprehensive view of animal resilience, the challenge is to merge knowledge and information from different dimensions of animal adaptive capacities. Recent works have shown the interest of combining different metrics/indicators of resilience (Llonch et al., 2020). Adriaens et al. (2020) used various sensor features related to milk production and activity to compute a resilience index for each dairy cow. Ben Abdelkrim (2021c) used body weight and milk yield deviations to reveal 3 profiles of responses to perturbations. Højsgaard and Friggens (2010) showed how multiple time-series indicators could be combined for improved detection of degree of mastitis. A second aspect in interpreting multiple time-series is the use of a theoretical framework, reflecting assumptions on underlying mechanisms and potential interactions between biological functions, which are behind the measured traits. Having such biological background, as it is the case in hybrid models, is paramount to account for potential trade-offs among functions and genotype by environment, which are key issues in implementing breeding program or management strategies to improve resilience in farm animals interactions (Puillet et al., 2021).

Another aspect to be considered is the capacity of real-time models to predict health problems early enough, before the decrease of animal production performance (Friggens et al., 2007). In other words, the model should be able to detect preclinical signs of the problems. In this respect, (Wagner et al.,

2021) showed that the use of longitudinal traits related to animal behaviour is useful, to predict preclinical signs of health problems. Moreover, their model considered the circadian cycle as a mechanism of cows' behaviour and the combination of such mechanism with an adequate machine learning approach helped at early detection of health problems in different farms used in their study.

Considering the case studies discussed in this work, solutions have been suggested for the determination of the expected trajectory in cases of (i) post treatment of data, with or without knowledge on underlying mechanisms (case studies 1 and 2, respectively), and (ii) in case of real time treatment of data when knowledge is available (case study 3). The question is how one can handle the case of real time treatment of data when knowledge on underlying mechanisms or the shape of the theoretical trajectory is not available (case study 4). In such cases, one way is to make assumptions on the shape of the expected trajectory. In the case study developed in example 4, the expected curve has been assumed as a constant value. Although making assumptions for well-studied variables, such as body weight or milk yield may be possible, it is seldom feasible for other variables such as animal behaviour. In the latter cases, approaches based on machine learning, which are purely data-driven, can be useful. For example, (Sun et al., 2010) used the neural network for prediction of mastitis risk. (Warner et al., 2020) tested the usefulness of a machine learning approach based on decision tree induction for the detection of dairy herds at high risk of lameness. Morota et al (2018) provides a complete overview on the use of machine learning to analyse big data in precision agriculture. The point in such approaches is to provide a training dataset with enough data to select the best statistical model and enable the predictions on the test dataset.

To date, machine learning approaches enable the prediction of risks at individual scale (detection of perturbations). With the increase in the use of sensors on farms, and in the context of studying animal resilience capacity, we can expect more informative results on the types of the problem (eg. mastitis, lameness, etc), and, most of all, on the resilience capacity of the animal. Considering Figure 1, the question is on the possibility of predicting the shape of the response given the historical data. This latter helps the farmer to decide whether or not pharmaceutical or other interventions are required for the animal to recover, or if the animal is able to recover by its own resources. However, as it is shown in this paper, resilience capacity is not a directly measurable feature and examples to quantify this characteristic were developed (case studies 1 and 2). Therefore, to go in this direction, new approaches should be developed to consider indirect measures of resilience and prediction of adaptive capacity in machine learning approaches. Ellis et al. (2020) explained that a better use of machine learning approach becomes possible when they are used together with concept-based approaches. Tedeschi et al. (2021) highlight the importance of hybridation of artificial intelligence methods with mechanistic models for the optimization of information extracted from PLF data, to go further in sustainability of animal production with respect to other animal functions.

Altogether, both data-driven and concept-driven approaches are discussed to detect health problems and to quantify resilience capacity at individual scale. Although the examples presented here are not exhaustive, they highlight the usefulness of each of the approaches. The availability of high frequency performance data enables the quantification of animal resilience at individual scale. The use of hybrid models seems promising for predicting this trait in real time.

Data and model availability.

The R code of the examples are available at <https://quantanimal.github.io/>.

Author ORCIDs

Taghipoor M <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5979-1578>

Pastell M <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5810-4801>

Martin O <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7375-2850>

Nguyen ba H <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2036-6486>

van Milgen J <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6131-5255>

Doesch-Wilson A <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2658-6973>

Loncke C <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5551-8542>

Puillet L <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2358-7302>

Muñoz-Tamayo R <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9266-4132>

Author contributions

MT drafted the manuscript, RMT and MP drafted the section on real time treatment of data. MT, MP and RMT developed the code of the case studies. All authors contributed to a critical revision of the manuscript and approved the final version.

Declaration of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Acknowledgment

The idea of this manuscript was firstly discussed in the doctoral module “robustness from a woolly concept to operational measures” supported by French alliance Agreenium. MT is grateful Dr. Isabelle Veissier for the stimulating discussions on the analysis of sensors data. The preprint of this article is deposited in Zenodo public repository.

Financial support statement

None

References

Ben Abdelkrim A, Puillet L, Gomes P and Martin O 2021a. Lactation curve model with explicit representation of perturbations as a phenotyping tool for dairy livestock precision farming. *Animal* 15, 100074.

Ben Abdelkrim A, Tribout T, Martin O, Boichard D, Ducrocq V and Friggens NCC 2021b. Exploring simultaneous perturbation profiles in milk yield and body weight reveals a diversity of animal responses and new opportunities to identify resilience proxies. *Journal of Dairy Science* 104, 459–470.

Adriaens I, Friggens NC, Ouweltjes W, Scott H, Aernouts B and Statham J 2020. Productive life span and resilience rank can be predicted from on-farm first-parity sensor time series but not using a common equation across farms. *Journal of Dairy Science* 103, 7155–7171.

Astrom KJ and Murray RM 2008. *Feedback Systems: An Introduction for Scientists and Engineers*. Princeton University Press, USA.

Benjamin M and Yik S 2019. Precision Livestock Farming in Swine Welfare: A Review for Swine Practitioners. *Animals* 9, 133.

Berghof TVL, Bovenhuis H and Mulder HA 2019a. Body Weight Deviations as Indicator for Resilience in Layer Chickens. *Frontiers in Genetics* 10.

Berghof TVL, Poppe M and Mulder HA 2019b. Opportunities to Improve Resilience in Animal Breeding Programs. *Frontiers in Genetics* 9, 1–15.

- Caja G, Castro-Costa A, Salama AAK, Oliver J, Baratta M, Ferrer C and Knight CH 2020. Sensing solutions for improving the performance, health and wellbeing of small ruminants. *Journal of Dairy Research* 87, 34–46.
- Chen L, Bernard O, Bastin G and Angelov P 2000. Hybrid modelling of biotechnological processes using neural networks. *Control Engineering Practice* 8, 821–827.
- Codrea MC, Højsgaard S and Friggens NC 2011. Differential smoothing of time-series measurements to identify disturbances in performance and quantify animal response characteristics: An example using milk yield profiles in dairy cows. *Journal of Animal Science* 89, 3089–3098.
- Colditz IG and Hine BC 2016. Resilience in farm animals : Biology , management , breeding and implications for animal welfare Resilience in farm animals : biology , management , breeding and implications for animal welfare.
- Dochain D 2003. State and parameter estimation in chemical and biochemical processes: a tutorial. *Journal of Process Control* 13, 801–818.
- Doeschl-Wilson AB 2011. The role of mathematical models of host-pathogen interactions for livestock health and production - A review. *Animal* 5, 895–910.
- Doeschl-Wilson AB, Brindle W, Emmans G and Kyriazakis I 2009. Unravelling the Relationship between Animal Growth and Immune Response during Micro-Parasitic Infections. *PLoS ONE* 4, e7508.
- Doeschl-Wilson AB, Knap PW, Kinghorn BP and Van Der Steen HAM 2007. Using mechanistic animal growth models to estimate genetic parameters of biological traits. *Animal* 1, 489–499.
- Dominiak KN and Kristensen AR 2017. Prioritizing alarms from sensor-based detection models in livestock production - A review on model performance and alarm reducing methods. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture* 133, 46–67.
- Dumont B, González-García E, Thomas M, Fortun-Lamothe L, Ducrot C, Dourmad JY and Tichit M 2014. Forty research issues for the redesign of animal production systems in the 21st century. *Animal* 8, 1382–1393.
- Ellis JL, Jacobs M, Dijkstra J, van Laar H, Cant JP, Tulpan D and Ferguson N 2020. Review: Synergy between mechanistic modelling and data-driven models for modern animal production systems in the era of big data. *Animal* 14, s223–s237.
- Friggens NC, Adriaens I, Boré R, Cozzi G, Jurquet J, Kamphuis C, Leiber F, Lora I, Sakowski T, Statham J and De Haas Y 2022. Resilience: reference measures based on longer-term consequences are needed to unlock the potential of precision livestock farming technologies for quantifying this trait. *Peer Community Journal* 2, e38.
- Friggens N, Bjerring M, Ridder C, Hjsgaard S and Larsen T 2008. Improved Detection of Reproductive Status in Dairy Cows Using Milk Progesterone Measurements. *Reproduction in Domestic Animals* 43, 113–121.
- Friggens NC, Chagunda MGG, Bjerring M, Ridder C, Hojsgaard S and Larsen T 2007. Estimating Degree of Mastitis from Time-Series Measurements in Milk: A Test of a Model Based on Lactate Dehydrogenase Measurements. *Journal of Dairy Science* 90, 5415–5427.
- Friggens NC, Duvaux-Ponter C, Etienne MP, Mary-Huard T and Schmidely P 2016. Characterizing individual differences in animal responses to a nutritional challenge: Toward improved robustness measures. *Journal of Dairy Science* 99, 2704–2718.
- Golubev A 2009. How could the Gompertz-Makeham law evolve. *Journal of Theoretical Biology*.

Gómez Y, Stygar AH, Boumans IJMM, Bokkers EAM, Pedersen LJ, Niemi JK, Pastell M, Manteca X and Llonch P 2021. A Systematic Review on Validated Precision Livestock Farming Technologies for Pig Production and Its Potential to Assess Animal Welfare. *Frontiers in Veterinary Science* 8, 492.

González LA, Kyriazakis I and Tedeschi LO 2018. Review : Precision nutrition of ruminants : approaches , challenges and potential gains.

Gustafsson F 2000. Adaptive Filtering and Change Detection.

Halachmi I, Guarino M, Bewley J and Pastell M 2019. Smart Animal Agriculture: Application of Real-Time Sensors to Improve Animal Well-Being and Production. *Annual Review of Animal Biosciences* 7, 403–425.

Højsgaard S and Friggens NC 2010. Quantifying degree of mastitis from common trends in a panel of indicators for mastitis in dairy cows. *Journal of Dairy Science* 93, 582–592.

Ingrisch J and Bahn M 2018. Towards a Comparable Quantification of Resilience. 251–259.

Islam ZU, Bishop SC, Savill NJ, Rowland RRR, Lunney JK, Tribble B and Doeschl-Wilson AB 2013. Quantitative Analysis of Porcine Reproductive and Respiratory Syndrome (PRRS) Viremia Profiles from Experimental Infection: A Statistical Modelling Approach. *PLoS ONE* 8, e83567.

Jørgensen CH, Kristensen AR, Østergaard S and Bennedsgaard TW 2016. Use of inline measures of l-lactate dehydrogenase for classification of posttreatment mammary *Staphylococcus aureus* infection status in dairy cows. *Journal of Dairy Science* 99, 8375–8383.

Kamphuis C, Mollenhorst H, Heesterbeek JAPAPP and Hogeveen H 2010. Detection of clinical mastitis with sensor data from automatic milking systems is improved by using decision-tree induction. *Journal of Dairy Science* 93, 3616–3627.

Knap PW and Doeschl-Wilson A 2020. Why breed disease-resilient livestock, and how? *Genetics Selection Evolution* 52, 60.

Lema-Perez L, Muñoz-Tamayo R, Garcia-Tirado J and Alvarez H 2019. On parameter interpretability of phenomenological-based semiphysical models in biology. *Informatics in Medicine Unlocked* 15, 100158.

Lewis RM and Emmans GC 2020. The relationship between feed intake and liveweight in domestic animals. *Journal of Animal Science* 98.

Llonch P, Hoffmann G, Bodas R, Mirbach D, Verwer C and Haskell MJ 2020. Opinion paper: Measuring livestock robustness and resilience: are we on the right track? *Animal* 14, 667–669.

Macé T, Gonzalez Garcia E, Kövér G, Hazard D and Taghipoor M 2020. PhenoBR, a model to phenotype body condition dynamics in meat sheep. Zenodo

Martin O and Sauvant D 2010. A teleonomic model describing performance (body, milk and intake) during growth and over repeated reproductive cycles throughout the lifespan of dairy cattle. 2. Voluntary intake and energy partitioning. *Animal : an international journal of animal bioscience* 4, 2048–2056.

van Milgen J, Valancogne A, Dubois S, Dourmad J-Y, Sève B and Noblet J 2008. InraPorc: A model and decision support tool for the nutrition of growing pigs. *Animal Feed Science and Technology* 143, 387–405.

Morota G, Ventura R V., Silva FF, Koyama M, Samodha C, Fernando SC and Samodha C 2018. Big data analytics and precision animal agriculture symposium: Machine learning and data mining advance predictive big data analysis in precision animal agriculture. *Journal of Animal Science* 96, 1540–1550.

Mulder HA and Rashidi H 2017. Selection on resilience improves disease resistance and tolerance to infections. *Journal of Animal Science* 95.

Muñoz-Tamayo R, Nielsen BL, Gagaoua M, Gondret F, Krause ET, Morgavi DP, Olsson IAS, Pastell M, Taghipoor M, Tedeschi L, Veissier I and Nawroth C 2022. Seven steps to enhance Open Science practices in animal science. *PNAS Nexus* 1, pgac106.

Muñoz-Tamayo R, Puillet L, Daniel JB, Sauvart D, Martin O, Taghipoor M and Blavy P 2018. Review: To be or not to be an identifiable model. Is this a relevant question in animal science modelling? *Animal* 12, 701–712.

Nguyen-Ba H, Milgen J Van and Taghipoor M 2019. A procedure to quantify the feed intake response of growing pigs to perturbations. 1–8.

Nguyen-Ba H, van Milgen J, Taghipoor M, Milgen J Van and Taghipoor M 2020. A procedure to quantify the feed intake response of growing pigs to perturbations. *animal* 14, 253–260.

Norberg E, Korsgaard IR, Sloth KHM and Løvendahl P 2008. Time-series models on somatic cell score improve detection of mastitis. *Acta Agriculturae Scandinavica, Section A - Animal Science* 58, 165–169.

Van Nuffel A, Zwervaegher I, Van Weyenberg S, Pastell M, Thorup V, Bahr C, Sonck B and Saeys W 2015. Lameness Detection in Dairy Cows: Part 2. Use of Sensors to Automatically Register Changes in Locomotion or Behavior. *Animals* 5, 861–885.

Petris G, Petrone S and Campagnoli P 2009. Dynamic linear models. In *Dynamic linear models with R*, pp. 31–84. Springer.

Poppe M, Veerkamp RF, van Pelt ML and Mulder HA 2020. Exploration of variance, autocorrelation, and skewness of deviations from lactation curves as resilience indicators for breeding. *Journal of Dairy Science* 103, 1667–1684.

Puillet L, Ducrocq V, Friggens NC and Amer PR 2021. Exploring underlying drivers of genotype by environment interactions in feed efficiency traits for dairy cattle with a mechanistic model involving energy acquisition and allocation. *Journal of Dairy Science* 104, 5805–5816.

Puillet L, Réale D and Friggens NC 2016. Disentangling the relative roles of resource acquisition and allocation on animal feed efficiency: insights from a dairy cow model. *Genetics Selection Evolution* 48, 72.

Ramsay JO and Silverman BWW 2002. *Applied Functional Data Analysis, methods and case studies*.

Revilla M, Friggens NC, Broudiscou LP, Lemonnier G, Blanc F, Ravon L, Mercat MJ, Billon Y, Rogel-Gaillard C, Le Floch N, Estellé J and Muñoz-Tamayo R 2019. Towards the quantitative characterisation of piglets' robustness to weaning: a modelling approach. *animal*, 1–11.

Rutter SM 2014. Smart technologies for detecting animal welfare status and delivering health remedies for rangeland systems. *Revue Scientifique et Technique de l'OIE* 33, 181–187.

Sadoul B, Martin O, Prunet P and Friggens NC 2015. On the Use of a Simple Physical System Analogy to Study Robustness Features in Animal Sciences. *PLOS ONE* 10, e0137333.

Sandberg FB, Emmans GC and Kyriazakis I 2006. A model for predicting feed intake of growing animals during exposure to pathogens. *Journal of Animal Science* 84, 1552–1566.

Sauvart D and Martin O 2010. Robustesse, rusticité, flexibilité, plasticité... les nouveaux critères de qualité des animaux et des systèmes d'élevage: définitions systémique et biologique des différents concepts. *INRA Prod. Anim.* 23, 5–10.

- Scheffer M, Bolhuis JE, Borsboom D, Buchman TG, Gijzel SMW, Goulson D, Kammenga JE, Kemp B, van de Leemput IA, Levin S, Martin CM, Melis RJF, van Nes EH, Romero LM and Olde Rikkert MGM 2018. Quantifying resilience of humans and other animals. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 115, 11883–11890.
- Schulin-Zeuthen M, Kebreab E, Dijkstra J, Lopez S, Bannink A, Darmani Kuhl H, Thornley JHM and France J 2008. A comparison of the Schumacher with other functions for describing growth in pigs. *Animal Feed Science and Technology* 143, 314–327.
- Stygar AH, Dolecheck KA and Kristensen AR 2018. Analyses of body weight patterns in growing pigs: a new view on body weight in pigs for frequent monitoring. *Animal* 12, 295–302.
- Stygar AH, Gómez Y, Berteselli G V., Dalla Costa E, Canali E, Niemi JK, Llonch P and Pastell M 2021. A Systematic Review on Commercially Available and Validated Sensor Technologies for Welfare Assessment of Dairy Cattle. *Frontiers in Veterinary Science* 8.
- Sun Z, Samarasinghe S and Jago J 2010. Detection of mastitis and its stage of progression by automatic milking systems using artificial neural networks. *Journal of Dairy Research* 77, 168–175.
- Taghipoor M, Brossard L and van Milgen J 2017. Characterization of growing pigs' adaptive response when faced with environmental perturbations. *Journées de la recherche porcine*.
- Tedeschi LO 2019. ASN-ASAS SYMPOSIUM: FUTURE OF DATA ANALYTICS IN NUTRITION: Mathematical modeling in ruminant nutrition: approaches and paradigms, extant models, and thoughts for upcoming predictive analytics^{1,2}. *Journal of Animal Science* 97, 1921–1944.
- Tedeschi LO, Greenwood PL and Halachmi I 2021. Advancements in sensor technology and decision support intelligent tools to assist smart livestock farming. *Journal of Animal Science* 99.
- Todman LC, Fraser FC, Corstanje R, Deeks LK, Harris JA, Pawlett M, Ritz K and Whitmore AP 2016. Defining and quantifying the resilience of responses to disturbance: A conceptual and modelling approach from soil science. *Scientific Reports* 6, 1–12.
- Vargas-Villamil LM, Tedeschi LO, Medina-Peralta S, Izquierdo-Reyes F, Navarro-Alberto J and González-Garduño R 2020. A multi-inverse approach for a holistic understanding of applied animal science systems. *Animal*.
- Wagner N, Mialon M-M, Sloth KH, Lardy R, Ledoux D, Silberberg M, de Boyer des Roches A and Veissier I 2021. Detection of changes in the circadian rhythm of cattle in relation to disease, stress, and reproductive events. *Methods* 186, 14–21.
- Warner D, Vasseur E, Lefebvre DM and Lacroix R 2020. A machine learning based decision aid for lameness in dairy herds using farm-based records. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture* 169, 105193.
- Wellock IJ, Emmans GC and Kyriazakis I 1998. Predicting the consequences of social stressors on pig food intake and performance 1. 2995–3007.
- Werkheiser I 2018. Precision Livestock Farming and Farmers' Duties to Livestock. *Journal of Agricultural and Environmental Ethics* 31, 181–195.
- West M and Harrison J 1997. *Bayesian Forecasting and Dynamic Models* (2nd Ed.). Springer-Verlag, Berlin, Heidelberg.
- Whittemore CT 1986. An approach to pig growth modeling. *Journal of animal science* v. 63.
- Whittemore CT and Fawcett RH 1976. Theoretical aspects of a flexible model to stimulate protein and lipid growth in pigs. *Animal Science* 22, 87–96.

Wolfert S, Ge L, Verdouw C and Bogaardt MJ 2017. Big Data in Smart Farming – A review. *Agricultural Systems* 153, 69–80.

Wood PDP 1967. Algebraic Model of the Lactation Curve in Cattle. *Nature* 216, 164–165.

Yu H, Milgen J, Knol E, Fernando R and Dekkers JC 2021. 32 A Bayesian Hierarchical Model to Integrate Growth Models into Genomic Evaluation of Pigs. *Journal of Animal Science* 99, 18–19.

Tables

Table 1. List of potential variables to describe and quantify animal resilience.

	Definition	Examples
Magnitude of perturbation	Maximum of the difference between the theoretical trajectory of performance and the actual perturbed performance	(Codrea et al., 2011) Dairy cows
Time of recovery	The time between the minimum value of performance reached and the time of complete recovery (return to the theoretical trajectory).	(Sadoul et al., 2015) Rainbow trout
Surface	The area between the theoretical trajectory and the actual performance during the perturbation interval	(Revilla et al., 2019) Piglet
Intensity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Speed of the decrease during the collapse phase speed of the increase during the recovery phase 	(Friggens et al., 2016; Macé et al., 2020; Ben Abdelkrim et al., 2021a) Meat sheep, dairy goats, dairy cows
Other dynamic indicator of resilience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Negative residuals based on estimation of an expected curve of performance Number of days with negative residuals Variance / natural logarithm transformed variance Temporal auto-correlation / lag-1 auto-correlation Skewness Cross correlation (between elements of the system) 	(Adriaens et al., 2020) (Scheffer et al., 2018) (animals and humans) (Poppe et al., 2020) dairy cows (Berghof et al., 2019b) laying hens

Table 2. Quantification of the animal’s response to two perturbations of the case study 2. A , h and ΔT are the area under the perturbed curve, the maximum effect of the perturbation and the time duration of the perturbation, respectively.

	A (kg)	h (kg)	ΔT (day)
Perturbation 1	5.56	0.29	26
Perturbation 2	3.32	0.11	19

List of figures captions

Figure 1. The response of three animals to a given perturbation. Animals’ observable response started at T1. The recovery started at T2. Animal **a** has a largest decrease in performance but recovers faster, while animal **b** and **c** have a smallest decrease in performance but they recover later. Moreover, animal **c** seems to compensate for the loose of performance. It is therefore necessary to define metrics for animal adaptive response to phenotype animals based on same criteria.

Figure 2. Difference in the concept of forward and inverse problem. a. Forward problem is the use of mechanistic models to predict the response of the animal (outputs) to a stimuli (inputs), given the animal characteristics (parameters) and a model structure (representation of underlying mechanisms or input-output behaviour). b. In the case of inverse problem, the dynamic data of model outputs can

be measured. Then given these data, and model structure, the user can estimate the characteristic of the animal (model parameters), using an adequate optimization procedure.

Figure 3. Hypothetic example of animal response to two different perturbations. Two consecutive perturbations occurred at $t_1^b = 10$ and $t_2^b = 75$, and were over at $t_1^e = 25$ and $t_2^e = 85$ days of age. Parameters of resistance (k_{1i}, k_{2i}) are (0.05, 0.15) for the first perturbation and (0.1, 0.05) for the second. One can easily realize that the animal had a better capacity to resist faced with the first perturbation, while the capacity of resilience was better in the second perturbation. Moreover, compared to the second perturbation (10 days), the animal took more time to start the recovery period (15 days).

Figure 4. Estimation of animal's performance using differential smoothing. The upper graph shows the estimated function against (black curve) observation (dot). The lower graph shows the derivative of the estimated function. Zeros of derivatives are associated to maximums and minimums of the function. The blue line on the upper graph shows the expected performance of the animal, which is assumed to be 1. A_i, h_i and ΔT_i are the area under the perturbed curve, the maximum effect of the perturbation and the time length of the perturbation, respectively.

Figure 5. A. Comparison of the real online trajectory of body weight (γ) (•) against the estimated trajectory ($\hat{\gamma}$) by the observer (solid line). B. Estimated trajectory $\hat{\varphi}$ by the observer (solid line) compared with the real trajectory φ (•). Note that in practice the real trajectory φ is unknown. In the example, we can plot it because it was set by construction.

Figure 6. Example of using switching model for detecting perturbations. The series is filtered using two different filters: 1st order model representing unperturbed dynamics and 2nd order model representing perturbed dynamics. The second panel shows the posterior probability for each model being the correct at time t and the bottom panel shows the estimated slope based on the second order model.

Figure 7. Hybrid modelling approach takes advantage of both data- and concept-driven models to extract the maximum information from existing data.